
CONTENT MARKETING AND CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

The proliferation and extensive application of content marketing in the digital age has prompted numerous scholarly investigations into its impact on customers' purchasing behaviours across diverse sectors. This study investigates the influence of content marketing on consumer buying behaviour for cosmetic products in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The primary objective was to explore the effects of infographics, blogs, and videos on consumer buying behaviour for cosmetic products. The survey research design was employed. A convenience sampling technique was used to gathered data from 384 customers using a structured questionnaire. Subsequently, descriptive analysis was conducted on the collected data, and the study's hypotheses were tested utilising the simple linear regression technique. Findings from the first hypothesis test indicated that infographics have a significant positive influence on consumers' buying behaviour for cosmetics. The findings also showed that blogs have a significant positive effect on consumers' buying behaviour for cosmetic products. Furthermore, the findings revealed that videos have a significant positive influence on consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics in the Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State. As a result, this research suggests, among others, that firms should distribute infographics across various digital platforms, including social media, websites, and email newsletters to maximise reach and engagement. In addition, acknowledging the constraints of this study, scholars have been encouraged to perform longitudinal studies to examine how consumer attitudes towards content marketing and purchasing behaviour evolve over time.

Keywords: Content marketing, infographics, blogs, videos, consumer buying behaviour

Introduction

The proliferation of content delivery platforms, such as blogs, podcasts, videos, and webinars, has given organisations various channels through which they can connect with consumers and deliver messages in more personalised and interactive ways. Such an evolution has led to a decrease in the effectiveness of traditional marketing strategies in capturing and maintaining audience attention. Hence, content marketing has emerged as a strategic approach for organisations to engage with their target audiences by providing relevant content that focuses on creating and distributing educational, informative, and entertaining information with the aim of building brand awareness, establishing thought leadership, and ultimately driving consumer buying decisions (Etuk *et al.*, 2025; Ewah *et al.*, 2021).

One of the defining characteristics of content marketing is its emphasis on providing value to the audience rather than solely focusing on promoting products or services. By delivering content that addresses the needs, interests, and wants of their target audience, organisations can establish trust, which leads to stronger relationships and increased brand loyalty (Duffett, 2015). Content marketing encompasses a wide array of dimensions, including blog posts, articles, videos, infographics, podcasts, and social media posts tailored to the preferences and behaviours of diverse consumer segments (Kapoor *et al.*, 2018). This diversity allows organisations to craft engaging narratives and deliver messages in a manner that echoes with their target audience, fostering deeper emotional connections and brand loyalty (Muntinga *et al.*, 2011). In this study, we used infographics, blogs, and videos as dimensions of content marketing to measure consumer buying behaviour.

Infographics play a crucial role in content marketing by acting as visual tools that set the tone, improve readability, and enhance overall design. They effectively summarise the evolution of content marketing by presenting key milestones and trends clearly and concisely. Blogs have become integral to content marketing strategies, serving as platforms for sharing information, opinions, and experiences digitally. In today's digital landscape, video content has emerged as a dominant medium, radically changing the way people consume and communicate information. Its origin can be traced back to early experiments in motion picture technology in the late 19th century, which laid the foundation for widespread adoption in the 21st century (Matusitz, 2021).

Consumer purchase behaviour is the process by which people or groups choose to buy, use, and dispose of goods and services. Understanding this behaviour is essential for businesses, particularly in the cosmetics industry. Companies that understand the motives, preferences, and cultural influences that drive purchasing decisions can adjust their content marketing tactics to better satisfy the requirements and aspirations of their target audience, resulting in increased sales and profitability (Solomon, 2019).

Cosmetics have a long and rich history, dating back to ancient civilisations like Egypt, Greece, and Rome. These early societies not only used cosmetics for personal decoration but also gave them cultural and spiritual importance. Cosmetics were thought to have protective and magical properties in ancient Egypt, whereas they were emblems of wealth, luxury, and social position in ancient Greece and Rome (Rahmawati *et al.*, 2021).

Cosmetic organisations must develop content marketing, particularly for their products, with a thorough understanding of local consumer purchasing habits. Organisations

can build captivating storylines that appeal to Uyo's varied audience by leveraging cosmetics' rich heritage and connecting them to the present ambitions of its citizens. For example, content that highlights the cultural significance of old beauty practices while offering modern products that reflect these values can effectively engage consumers. Presenting cosmetics as a form of personal expression and empowerment can appeal to the growing youth force that is increasingly impacted by worldwide trends. Content marketing serves as a link between the past and the present, connecting the historical relevance of cosmetics to the current desires of consumers in Uyo Metropolis. Understanding and adapting to consumer buying behaviours allows cosmetic firms to increase market share and develop stronger ties with their audiences, resulting in long-term loyalty and success.

However, a survey of academic studies revealed a wealth of content marketing material that addressed a wide variety of marketable customer concerns. Some of these businesses have focused on how consumers will benefit from content marketing when using cosmetic products. Many research studies on content marketing have been undertaken, but none on the relationship between content marketing and consumer purchasing behaviour of cosmetics products in Akwa Ibom State. To this end, the main objective of this study was to examine the influence of content marketing and its underpinnings (infographics, blogs, and videos) on consumer buying behaviours for cosmetic products in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. In line with the objective of this study, the following hypotheses were formulated:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between infographic and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetic in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between blogs and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetic in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship between video and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetic in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Review of Related Literature

An Overview of Content Marketing

The digital revolution of the 21st century has significantly transformed content marketing, enabling businesses to reach and engage with their audiences on a global scale through various digital platforms, including blogs, social media, videos, podcasts, and more (Etuk *et al.*, 2025). Oladipo *et al.* (2020) define content marketing as the strategic use of digital content, such as blog posts, videos, social media updates, and podcasts, to connect with consumers, build brand awareness, and influence their purchase decisions. Content marketing involves the process of developing, distributing, and amplifying content that is designed to inform, engage, and persuade a targeted audience with the goal of driving profitable customer interactions and conversions (Lieb, 2011). Content marketing plays a crucial role in the digital age by enhancing brand visibility, fostering customer engagement, establishing thought leadership, driving website traffic and conversions, and offering cost-effective and measurable results for businesses.

Dimensions of Content Marketing

Infographics

Infographics are visual representations of data, information, or knowledge designed to convey complex concepts quickly and clearly (Udofia and Etim, 2021). The concept blends text, images, and graphics in a visually appealing format to make information more accessible and engaging to the audience. Infographics serve as a powerful tool for

communication, enabling individuals and organisations to present data-driven insights, tell compelling stories, and simplify intricate ideas for better understanding (Usani *et al.*, 2024).

Concept of Blogs

Handley *et al.* (2019) describe blogs as dynamic content hubs that allow creators to share insights, stories, and expertise with a global audience. Blogs are online platforms where individuals or organisations publish regular entries of commentary, information, or opinions on a variety of topics. They have evolved into versatile tools used for personal expression, professional branding, knowledge sharing, and marketing. Blogs, short for weblogs, are online platforms where individuals, organisations, or businesses regularly publish content in the form of articles, posts, or entries (Akpan and Ekpo, 2020). These entries are typically displayed in reverse chronological order, with the most recent content appearing first. Blogs serve various purposes, including personal expression, professional branding, knowledge sharing, and marketing. They often cover a wide range of topics, from personal experiences and hobbies to industry insights and educational resources.

Concept of Video

Video is a dynamic medium for visual communication that combines moving images, audio, and sometimes text to convey information, tell stories, and evoke emotions. In today's digital age, video content has become increasingly popular and accessible, with platforms like YouTube and social media streaming services driving its widespread adoption. From entertainment and education to marketing and journalism, video plays a significant role in shaping how people consume information and interact with content online (Oladipo *et al.*, 2020). Video content is commonly distributed and consumed through various platforms, including television, film, streaming services, social media, and online websites.

Consumer Buying Behaviour of Cosmetics

Understanding consumer behaviour in this context involves analysing the factors that influence consumers' choices, preferences, and purchases when it comes to cosmetics. The discussion includes psychological, social, cultural, and economic factors that impact how consumers perceive, evaluate, and select cosmetic products. Consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics refers to the processes and factors that influence individuals' decisions and actions when purchasing cosmetic products (Akinola *et al.*, 2021). This field of study examines the psychological, social, cultural, and economic factors that shape consumers' attitudes, preferences, and behaviours in relation to the selection, purchase, and use of cosmetics.

Theoretical Framework

The anchor theory for the study is the theory of planned behaviour, propounded by Ajzen in 1991. The theory posits that three fundamental components—attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control—collectively influence an individual's behavioural intentions. A principle of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) is that behavioural intention serves as the most immediate predictor of human social behaviour. Icek Ajzen developed this theory to enhance the predictive capacity of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by incorporating perceived behavioural control, which was absent in TRA. TPB has been utilised in research examining relationships among beliefs, attitudes, behavioural intentions, and behaviours across various fields, including marketing, advertising, public relations, healthcare, and sport management. The theory holds relevance to this study as it explains the factors that influence consumer buying behaviour, of which infographics, blogs

and videos are presumed as dimensions to predict consumer purchase behaviour of cosmetics products in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Empirical Framework

Koob (2021) conducted a study with the aim to investigate the context features determining content marketing effectiveness from a managerial perspective. The study adopted a survey research design. The questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection, and multiple regression analysis was used to measure the hypotheses formulated. The results indicated that clarity and commitment regarding content marketing strategy and production in line with the organization's target groups' content needs, as well as normative journalistic quality criteria, are context-related factors associated with higher content marketing effectiveness. Elald and Cifci (2021) carried out a study to investigate the effectiveness of using infographics on academic achievement. Findings revealed that using infographics in education has a positive effect on academic achievement, with a significant impact.

Chandra (2023) did a study to determine the impact of infographics on digital marketing campaigns: strengthening brand communication and reputation. The results showed that infographics with their visually appealing designs and share ability on social media platforms further expand the reach and impact of marketing campaigns. Chen *et al.* (2018) conducted a study to investigate the effects of social media marketing on customer satisfaction in e-commerce. The findings revealed a positive relationship between social media engagement and customer satisfaction.

Fadhil *et al.* (2022) carried out a study to investigate the impact of e-marketing channels (social media, blogs and e-mail) on online shopping behaviour of food item companies that are brand branches or official agencies in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq – Sulaimani city. The results indicated that social media and websites have the greatest influence on online consumer buying behaviour. It was also revealed that the correlation coefficient between consumer buying behaviour and electronic marketing is positive, while the sub-variables of social media and blogs have a stronger relationship with the dependent variable, unlike the sub-variable of blogs, which has a weak relation with the dependent variable.

Orzan *et al.* (2020) conducted an investigation to determine the impact of blogs on corporate marketing communication. Findings revealed that higher benefits from using a blog can lead to a brand awareness and brand loyalty enhancement favoured by community participation in product development, a corporate image enhanced by the trustful environment instalment and the company's participation in social responsibility campaigns, a more profound insight into consumers thoughts and actions mined through data from their comments, and a better information dissemination between the company and its stakeholders: customers, employees, shareholders, suppliers and partners.

Wang and Yang (2021) carried out a study to explore the impact mechanism of short video content marketing on consumer purchase intention. Findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between social media analytics and customer satisfaction, but it remains subject to the varied characteristics of external stakeholders. A study conducted by Hussin *et al.* (2021) examined the impact of current video advertisement practices on

consumer purchase intentions. The study revealed a strong connection between consumer purchase intention and factors such as ad attractiveness, ad persuasiveness, and ad awareness.

Most of the studies examined found that content marketing add significantly to consumer buying behaviour. In order to demonstrate the causality among the variables, a conceptual model was formulated and presented in Figure 1.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Source: Researcher’s Construct (2024)

Figure 1: Showing the conceptual framework of Content Marketing depicting the variables used on Consumer Buying Behaviour.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was used in this study. This design made it possible to use a questionnaire to collect information from the sample respondents. Geographically, the study was carried out in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The target population for this study were customers who purchase and consume cosmetic products in Uyo metropolis, which was statistically considered infinite. Given the nature of the population, the Topman formula for infinite population was used to determine an appropriate sample size of 384. For this study, the researchers employed the convenience sampling technique to select respondents for the study.

Primary data was obtained through the use of a questionnaire titled “Content marketing and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetic products in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State”. The questionnaire was self-developed by the researchers, and it was further divided into two sections. Section A consisted of demographic characteristics of the respondents, while Section B consisted of the main variables used in the study divided into four sub-sections related to each of the three independent variables and the dependent variable used in the study. The variables were measured on a 5-point Likert scale—strongly agreed, agreed, undecided, strongly disagreed, and disagreed—with values of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

The Cronbach alpha coefficient was used as a reliability parameter to determine the internal consistency of the instrument items in the study. An acceptable limit was between 0.5 and 0.8. Infographics had a reliability coefficient of 0.714, blogs had 0.661, and video had 0.691. Hence, the Cronbach's alpha of above 0.5 indicated internal consistency of items and was relied upon to explain causality between the variables. The use of descriptive analysis was employed in accessing respondents’ opinions with the use of frequency distribution tables and simple percentages. The simple regression analysis was also used to test for the

influence of content marketing proxies: infographics (X1), blogs (X2), and videos (X3) on the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics).

Data Presentation

A total of 384 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to customers who purchase and consume cosmetic products in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, and 300 copies were retrieved and found usable, giving a response rate of 78%. The responses were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 26). Table 1 presents the analysis of demographic variables.

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Respondents

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
<u>Age of respondents</u>		
18-25 years	75	25.0
26-35years	76	25.3
36-45 years	60	20.0
46yearsand Above	89	29.7
Total	300	100.0
<u>Gender of respondent</u>		
Male	139	46.3
Female	161	53.7
Total	300	100.0
<u>Occupation of Respondents</u>		
Student	75	25.0
Employed	76	25.3
Unemployed	60	20.0
Other	89	29.7
Total	300	100.0
<u>Frequently Purchased</u>		
Daily	58	19.3
Weekly	51	17.0
Monthly	59	19.7
Occasionally	70	23.3
Rarely	62	20.7
Total	300	100.0

Source: Compiled from Field Survey (2024).

Result on Table 1: shows that 89 respondents (29.7%) were within the age range of 46 years and above, which made up a larger proportion of the respondents who participated in the survey; this was closely followed by 76 respondents (25.3%) who were between the ages of 26 and 55 years, while 75 respondents (25.0%) fell between the age range of 18 and 25 years, and 60 respondents (20.0%) were the ages of 36 and 45 years. The table also indicates that 139 respondents (46.3%) were males and 161 respondents (53.7%) were females who participated in this study. The implication of this result is that, for any generalisations or strategic decisions based on this survey, the demographic skew towards younger and female respondents should be taken into account to ensure balanced and inclusive outcomes. The table summary also shows that 75 respondents (25.0%) were students, 76 respondents

(25.3%) were employed, 60 respondents (20.0%) were unemployed, and others who were not in this category were 89 respondents (29.7%). The table summary also indicates that 58 respondents (19.3%) who participated in the survey often purchased cosmetic products daily, 51 respondents (17.0%) purchased weekly, 59 respondents (19.7%) were monthly buyers, 70 respondents (23.3%) were occasional buyers, and 62 respondents (20.7%) rarely consumed cosmetic products.

Test of Hypotheses

As earlier stated in the methodology, all hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significant level. Results of the simple linear regression analysis are summarised on the tables.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between infographic and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2: Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression analysis showing the relationship between infographics and consumer buying behaviour.

	B₀	SE	B₁	t-value	Significant (2 tailed)
Constant	2.161	0.387		5.587	0.000
Independent Variable: Infographic	0.842	0.029	0.857	28.728	0.000
Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour					
R =	0.857 ^a				
R ² =	0.735				
Adjusted R-Square =	0.734				
Std. Error of estimate =	0.95305				
F-statistics =	825.318				
Probability (Significant p-value) =	0.000 ^b				

**significantly related at 5% (p<0.05). B₁= unstandardized beta, B₂= standardized beta, SE= standard error.*

Source: The Researcher's Computation (2024).

Table 2 shows that the independent variable infographic ($X_1 = In$) explained approximately 73% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour with an $R^2 = 0.735$. This means that infographics as a content marketing indicator was able to account for 73% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour, while 27% of the changes in the dependent variables could be attributed to factors not captured in the model. The result reveals that the relationship between infographic (In) and consumer buying behaviour (Cb) was very strong according to the $R = 0.857a$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.734$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a very strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

In addition, the F-ratio = 825.318 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that the infographic significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for infographic (In) had a statistically significant unstandardised coefficient of $\beta_{x_1} = 0.842$ and p-value = 0.000, indicating a positive

significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour. This finding can be interpreted that every unit change in the infographic will result in a 0.842 increase in consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the proposed simple linear regression equation:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e$$

$$Cb = a_0 + \beta_1 In + e$$

The resulting simple linear model is represented as:

$$Cb = 2.161 + 0.842X_1$$

$$Cb = 2.161 + 0.842In$$

However, since the significant p-value is less than 0.05 (Sig. p-value = 0.000 < 0.05), based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis earlier formulated to guide the study is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. It is therefore, concluded that there is a significant positive influence of infographic on consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between blogs and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression analysis showing the relationship between blogs and consumer buying behaviour.

	B₀	SE	B₁	t-value	Significant (2 tailed)
Constant	0.535	0.251		2.135	0.034
Independent Variable: Blogs	0.960	0.019	0.947	50.867	0.000
Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour					
R =	0.947 ^a				
R ² =	0.897				
Adjusted R-Square =	0.896				
Std. Error of estimate =	0.59465				
F-statistics =	2587.493				
Probability (Significant p-value) =	0.000 ^b				

**significantly related at 5% (p<0.05). B₁= unstandardized beta, B₂= standardized beta, SE= standard error.*

Source: The Researcher's Computation (2024).

Table 3 shows that the independent variable blogs (X₂=Bg) explained approximately 90% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour with an R²=0.897. This means that blogs, as a content marketing indicator, accounted for 90% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour, while 10% of the changes in the dependent variables could be attributed to factors not captured in the model. The result reveals that the relationship between blogs (Bg) and consumer buying behaviour (Cb) was very strong according to the R = 0.947a and adjusted R² = 0.896, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a very strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

In addition, the F-ratio = 2587.493 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that blogs significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for blogs (Bg) had a statistically significant unstandardized coefficient of $\beta_{x_2} = 0.960$ and p-value = 0.000, indicating a positive significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour. This finding can be interpreted that every unit change in blogs will result to a 0.960 increase in consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the proposed simple linear regression equation:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Cb = a_0 + \beta_2 Bg + e$$

The resulting simple linear model is represented as:

$$Cb = 0.535 + 0.960 X_2$$

$$Cb = 0.535 + 0.960 Bg$$

However, since the significant p-value is less than 0.05 (Sig. p-value = 0.000 < 0.05), based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis earlier formulated to guide the study is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Therefore, was concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between blogs and consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between video and consumer patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression analysis showing the relationship between video and consumer buying behaviour.

	B ₀	SE	B ₁	t-value	Significant (2 tailed)
Constant	0.322	0.129		2.490	0.013
Independent Variable: Video	0.977	0.010	0.986	100.338	0.000
Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour					
R =	0.986 ^a				
R ² =	0.971				
Adjusted R-Square =	0.971				
Std. Error of estimate =	0.31374				
F-statistics =	10067.810				
Probability (Significant p-value) =	0.000 ^b				

**significantly related at 5% (p < 0.05). B₁ = unstandardized beta, B₂ = standardized beta, SE = standard error.*

Source: The Researcher's Computation (2024).

Table 4 shows that the independent variable video (X₃=V_o) explained approximately 97% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour with an R²= 0.971. This means that

video, as a content marketing indicator, was able to account for 97% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour, while 3% of the changes in the dependent variables could be attributed to factors not captured by the model. The result reveals that the relationship between video (Vo) and consumer buying behaviour (Cb) was very strong according to the $R = 0.971$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.971$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a very strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

In addition, the F-ratio = 10067.810 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that the video significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for video (Vo) had a statistically significant unstandardised coefficient of $\beta_{X_3} = 0.977$ and p-value = 0.000, indicating a positive significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour. This finding can be interpreted as saying that every unit change in video will result in a 0.977 increase in consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the proposed simple linear regression equation:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$$

$$Cb = a_0 + \beta_3 Vo + e$$

The resulting simple linear model is represented as:

$$Cb = 0.322 + 0.977 X_3$$

$$Cb = 0.322 + 0.977 Vo$$

However, since the significant p-value is less than 0.05 (Sig. p-value = 0.000 < 0.05), based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis earlier formulated to guide the study is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. It is therefore, concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between video and consumer patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The main aim of this study was to ascertain the influence of content marketing on consumer buying behaviour for cosmetic products in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The indicators of content marketing were infographics, blog posts, and videos. Findings of the first hypothesis test indicated that infographics have a significant positive relationship with consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. According to the regression coefficient $R^2 = 0.735$, the regression model of this study is said to have a good explanatory power of the dependent variable. Thus, the independent variable = X_1 (infographic) explained approximately 74% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This means that the infographic was able to account for 74% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour towards cosmetics, while 26% of the changes in the dependent variables could be attributed to other factors not captured in the model. The resulting beta coefficient also showed that a unit change in infographics will lead to a corresponding increase in consumer buying behaviour towards cosmetics. This finding is in line with Elaldı and Cıfci (2021), whose study findings revealed that using infographics in education has a positive effect on academic achievement and the effect is at a large level.

Findings of the second hypothesis test indicated that there is a significant relationship between blogs and consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. According to the regression coefficient $R^2 = 0.897$, the regression model of this study is said to have a good explanatory power of the dependent variable. Thus, the independent variable = X_2 (blogs = Bg) explained approximately 90% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics. This means that blogs were able to account for 90% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics, while 10% could be attributed to factors not captured in the model. The resulting beta coefficient also showed that a unit change in blogs would lead to a corresponding increase in consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics. This finding is in agreement with Orzan *et al.* (2020), who highlight from their findings that higher benefits from using a blog can lead to a brand awareness and brand loyalty enhancement favoured by community participation in product development, a corporate image enhanced by the trustful environment instalment and the company's participation in social responsibility campaigns, a more profound insight into consumers thoughts and actions mined through data from their comments, and a better information dissemination between the company and its stakeholders: customers, employees, shareholders, suppliers and partners.

The result of the third hypothesis revealed that video has a significant positive relationship with consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. According to the regression coefficient $R^2 = 0.971$, the regression model of this study is said to have a good explanatory power of the dependent variable. Thus, the independent variable = X_3 (video = Vo) explained approximately 97% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This means that video was able to account for 97% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, while 3% of the changes could be attributed to other factors not captured in the model. The resulting beta coefficient also showed that a unit change in video will lead to a corresponding increase in consumer buying behaviour for cosmetics in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. This finding is in consent with Liu and Wang (2023), who emphasised in their study that when the product is highly involved, consumers do not pay more attention to short video content because they want to obtain more information, which leads to an increase in perceived value.

Conclusion and Business Implications

It is evident from the study's findings that when tested individually, infographics, blogs and video played a significant role in building consumer buying behaviour of cosmetics in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, and were significant positive predictors of consumer buying behaviour of cosmetic products in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Overall, understanding the diverse needs and preferences of consumers in Uyo Metropolis allows cosmetics organisations to tailor their marketing strategies effectively. By focusing on digital content, online reviews, and pricing, organisations can enhance their market presence, influence consumers' decisions, and drive successful outcomes in the competitive cosmetics industry.

Given the positive response to infographics, businesses should invest in creating high-quality, visually appealing infographics that highlight product features, benefits, and differentiators. Such graphics can improve consumer engagement and increase brand visibility. Blogs are an effective way to provide valuable information and influence purchasing decisions. Businesses should focus on producing diverse and relevant blog content, including product reviews, tutorials, and industry news, to attract and retain

customers. This strong preference for video content indicates that businesses should prioritise producing engaging videos that showcase product demonstrations, tutorials, and reviews. These videos can help build consumer trust and drive purchase decisions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Firms within the cosmetic industry should distribute infographics across various digital platforms, including social media, websites, and email newsletters, to maximise reach and engagement.
- ii. Firms should ensure that videos are informative, engaging, and visually appealing.
- iii. Firms should actively manage and respond to online reviews. Encourage satisfied customers to leave positive feedback and address any negative reviews transparently to maintain a positive brand image.

Suggestion for Further Studies

This study was limited in so many areas, like the research design used, which did not allow us to study the behaviour of respondents for a period of time. Therefore, we encourage researchers to conduct longitudinal studies that explore the evolution of consumer attitudes towards content marketing and purchasing behaviour over time. Such investigations can provide insights into trends and shifts in consumer preferences and the effectiveness of various content strategies over different periods. Conduct comparative studies among different geographic regions or cultural contexts to understand how cultural differences influence the effectiveness of content marketing strategies and consumer behaviour in the cosmetics industry.

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